

Synthesis of Steroidal Dithiolanes : Reaction of Ethane Dithiol with Saturated Steroidal Ketones

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The reaction of 5 α -cholestan-6-one (I) with ethane dithiol (BF₃-etherate as catalyst) provided 5 α -cholestan-6-one ethylene thioketal (V). Under similar reaction conditions 3 β -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (II), 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one (III) and 3 β -iodo-5 α -cholestan-6-one (IV) gave 3 β -acetoxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one ethylene thioketal (VI), 3 β -chloro-5 α -cholestan-6-one ethylene thioketal (VII) and 3 β -iodo-5 α -cholestan-6-one ethylene thioketal (VIII), respectively. Thioketal (V) on desulfurization with Raney nickel afforded 5 α -cholestane (IX). The structures of these compounds were established on the basis of their spectral properties, chemical transformations and comparison with authentic samples.

IN continuation of our previous work¹ we carried out the synthesis of some steroidal dithiolanes by the reaction of ethane dithiol with saturated steroidal ketones. Dithiolanes are more important on

account of their pharmacological potentialities²⁻⁴. A few steroidal dithioketals were tested for modest activity in a seroflocculation reaction with cancer sera⁵. These physiological observations prompted us to undertake the present work.

When 5 α -cholestan-6-one (I)⁶ was reacted with ethane dithiol in acetic acid, using BF₃-etherate as catalyst, 5 α -cholestan-6-one ethylene thioketal (V) was obtained.

The compound V analysed correctly for C₂₉H₅₀S₂ and exhibited a characteristic band at 680 cm⁻¹ (-C-S) in its ir spectrum. NMR spectrum showed a singlet at δ 3.21, which can be ascribed to four protons of thioketal ring (-S-CH₂-CH₂-S-). Formation of thioketal (V) was further supported by its desulfurization with Raney nickel, which provided 5 α -cholestane (IX) (identical m.p., tlc, ir and nmr with authentic sample)⁷.

Similar treatment of ketone II⁸ afforded VI, which was correctly analysed for C₃₁H₅₂O₂S₂. Its ir spectrum had bands at 1747, 1245, 1035 cm⁻¹ (O=C-CH₃) and 675 cm⁻¹ (-C-S). NMR spectrum showed a broad multiplet at δ 4.7 (C3- α H; W_{1/2}=14 Hz; axial), a singlet at δ 3.28 for

four thioketal ring protons (-S-CH₂-CH₂-S-) and another singlet at δ 2.08 (O=C-CH₃).

Compounds III and IV⁹, when subjected to similar reaction conditions, gave thioketals VII and VIII, respectively and their structures were quite compatible with the ir and nmr spectral data shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	IR ($\nu_{\max}$; cm ⁻¹)	NMR* (δ ppm)
VII	760 (C-Cl), 675 (C-S)	3.9 br,m (1H; C8- α H; W _{1/2} =16 Hz; axial), 3.25 s (4H, -S-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -S-).
VIII	680 (C-S), 510 (C-I)	4.16 br,m (1H, C8- α H; W _{1/2} =14 Hz; axial), 3.17 s (4H, -S-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -S-).

* C10 β -, C13 β - and side chain methyl protons appeared between δ 1.20 and 0.67.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were determined in KBr with a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer. NMR spectra were run in CDCl₃ on a Varian A60 instrument with TMS as the internal standard. TLC plates were coated with silica gel. A 20% aqueous solution of perchloric acid was used as the spraying agent. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent. NMR values are given in ppm (s=singlet; m=multiplet; br=broad; W_{1/2}=half band width).

5 α -Cholestan-6-one ethylene thioketal (V): A solution of ketone I⁶ (2.0 g) in acetic acid (60 ml) was treated with ethane dithiol (1 ml) and freshly distilled BF₃-etherate (2 ml) and left at room temp. for 1 hr. The solution was diluted with methanol (10 ml), poured into water and extracted with ether.

The ethereal layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Removal of the solvent yielded a noncrystallizable semisolid compound V (1.5 g). (Found : C, 75.27 ; H, 10.79. $C_{29}H_{50}S_2$ requires C, 75.32 ; H, 10.82%).

Desulfurization of V with Raney nickel : 5 α -cholestane (IX) : A solution of thioketal V (300 mg) in absolute ethanol (200 ml) was treated with Raney nickel (2 g) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 hr. The suspension was filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The compound thus obtained was recrystallized from acetone (85 mg), m.p. 81-82° (reported⁷ m.p. 80°) and was found similar to IX in all respects. (Found : C, 87.06 ; H, 12.88. $C_{27}H_{48}$ requires C, 87.10 ; H, 12.9%).

Reaction of ketones II, III and IV with ethane dithiol : Ketones II, III and IV with ethane dithiol

under the conditions described for ketone I, provided thioketals VI, VII and VIII, respectively. Melting points, yields and elemental analysis of these products are given in Table 2.

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TABLE 2

Compound	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)	
			C	H
VI	149-151	82	71.47 (71.54)	9.97 (10.0)
VII	149-145	85	70.05 (70.09)	9.85 (9.87)
VIII	180-181	81	59.18 (59.19)	8.29 (8.33)